

Wild Wild West of ICO's has come to end, Regulated Tokens (the year of TAO)

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Provide an overview of the ICO vs TAO.

2. Aim

Bring education to a fragmented market on state of ICO in 2018 as the introduction of TAO

According to the cryptocurrency statistics website Coinschedule, a total of 235 ICO's have raised over \$3.7 billion in 2017. There does not appear to be any slow down in this market as this seems to be the new flavour for companies raising money.

2018 will be even bigger for companies to utilize this new form of capital raising.

Our 4 hour program will cover:

1. Why the craze is global
2. Coin vs Token Why a Token
3. Types of Token
4. Framework for a Token Offering
5. Eco-system to get you started
6. Custom Report with the tools, and eco-system

3. Keywords:

ICO, TAO, STO, Security Token

Author biography

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Oscar is currently one of the Top 10 Global Thought Leaders in Equity Crowdfunding, a Top 5 Fintech Influencer, Top 10 Blockchain and a Top 50 InsureTech. He has published

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an eBook that has been downloaded in over 20 countries, and been distributed by partners worldwide.

Oscar is a featured speaker on Fintech, regulated, equity crowdfunding, compliance, shareholder management, investor relations, and transparency in the USA, Australia, UK, Germany, France, Netherlands, Canada, Singapore, Indonesia and China. He speaks to audiences covering alternative finance, equity crowdfunding, TAO, ICO/ITO, RegTech, insurance, banking, legal, and crowdfunding. Oscar also advises the world's leading research, accounting, law firms and insurance companies on the impact Blockchain, TAO, ICO, Fintech, RegTech, LegalTech, InsurTech and OrgTech is having in their business.

He is a member of the Crowdfunding Intermediary Regulatory Advocates (CFIRA) in the USA, and a contributing author to *The Fintech Book*, the world's first crowdsourced book on Fintech globally. He writes for Sharewise, Locavesting, Equities.com, Business.com, Crowdfund Insider, Crowdfund Beat, Bankless Times, and Agoracom.

Oscar has been recognized as one of the 10 most influential Hispanic Leaders in Canada. In May 2010, Oscar A. Jofre Jr. was recognized by the Rt. Hon. Stephen Harper for his accomplishments.

<http://www.marketwired.com/press-release/boardsuiter-corp-president-ceo-oscar-a-jofre-jr-recognized-rt-hon-stephen-harper-1272320.htm>

Oscar was awarded the Vision 2012 Business Man of the Year by the Toronto Hispanic Chamber of Commerce on September 2012.